

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Report detailing the communication and dissemination process conducted in nextGEMS with the analysis of its impact.

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WP10

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Executive summary

This deliverable details the activities conducted to implement the nextGEMS communication and dissemination plan. The main objective of communication and dissemination activities is to reach out to several audiences that can benefit from receiving periodic updates about the project and its scientific advancements. The targeted audiences of the nextGEMS communication and dissemination plan covered a wide range of profiles: from the most technical—the scientific community and technical profiles related to High Performance Computing (HPC)—, to policy and society. Communication and dissemination activities are a good platform to start bridging the science-policy and science-practice interfaces, and we ensured that the wide range of activities deployed supported their strengthening. Besides using standard science communication approaches, such as peer-reviewed articles, participation at conferences, social media and the project website, nextGEMS also explored and applied innovative communication and dissemination approaches and tools. These include Vlogs (the video communication), science explainers and, on the scientific side implementing participatory approaches with stakeholders, storylines.

The communication and dissemination activities are part of WP10 and the Storms & Society theme, and the main three partners responsible for its implementation are the Max-Planck-Institute für Meteorologie (MPI-M), Latest Thinking (LT) and the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). However, the activities have been deployed in close collaboration with all consortium members and project participants.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	yes

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	yes
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	yes
Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)	yes

Synergies

Communication activities within nextGEMS were never standalone efforts but deeply integrated into the project's broader structure and scientific workflow. Rather than being delegated, communication was embraced as a shared responsibility across all work packages. Researchers themselves were not just passive subjects of communication but active participants, co-developing content, appearing in videos, writing blog posts, and presenting at events. This integrated approach ensured that communication outputs were grounded in real scientific developments and tailored to diverse audiences with authenticity and depth. Tools such as storylines, science explainers, and vlogs were created collaboratively, reflecting the work and voices of scientists from across the consortium. The result was a communication strategy that mirrored the interdisciplinary and co-creative spirit of nextGEMS—enhancing visibility, impact, and uptake of project outcomes across research, policy, and society.

1. Introduction

At the outset of the project, WP10 developed a Communication and Dissemination Plan (Deliverable D10.2, Baulenas and Bojovic, 2022), grounded in the principles of visibility, transparency, plurality, and usability (Norström et al., 2020). These principles have continued to guide nextGEMS communication and dissemination activities throughout the project.

- **Visibility:** this principle has been achieved by deploying several communication and dissemination products, to give visibility to the project results.
- **Transparency:** the material produced moved alongside the scientific developments of the projects, showing the inception, challenges and solutions implemented to achieve the overall objectives of nextGEMS.
- **Plurality:** the project has adopted a gender- and diversity-sensitive approach in stakeholder engagement, communication strategies, and the dissemination of information.
- **Usability:** the principle of usability was made actionable with the goal to make the science produced in nextGEMS accessible to a wide range of profiles, to ultimately benefit its flexibility.

In alignment with EU guidelines for best practices in project communication, nextGEMS allocated significant resources to communication and dissemination activities. These efforts are central to both WP10 and the Storms & Society theme. However, these activities have not only been central for WP10, but have involved all consortium partners who have been engaged and actively participated in their design and deployment. This report details the communication and dissemination activities that took place during the project.

2. The importance of science communication and dissemination in research projects

Communication and dissemination activities are critical components of research projects, contributing to a wide range of desirable outcomes such as enhancing the visibility of research, fostering public engagement, and facilitating the practical application of scientific findings. Far from being auxiliary tasks, these activities are integral to the research process itself, as they bridge the gap between scientific communities, policymakers, and society at large. When strategically planned and effectively executed, communication and dissemination efforts can amplify societal impact, inform policy development, and foster broader public understanding of complex scientific issues.

According to science communication scholars, one of the core functions of dissemination is to make research outputs accessible and visible to a wide array of stakeholders, including decision-makers and the general public. Studies have shown that visibility increases significantly when communication efforts are strategically directed toward both academic and non-academic audiences (Marín-González et al., 2017; Mea et al., 2016). Due to the particularities of nextGEMS, a project devoted to performing the first multi-decadal simulations at km-scale, reaching the wider public was one of the particular challenges, because of the high technical

and scientific complexities that it represents. Nonetheless, the expertise of the team deploying these activities implemented purposeful strategies to overcome this challenge. A very good example of this, can be found in the first video that presented the nextGEMS project to a broad audience ([nextGEMS in a nutshell](#)).

Effective communication requires a broad toolkit. Research projects now employ a mix of traditional methods—such as peer-reviewed publications, policy briefs, and workshops—and newer, more dynamic tools like social media, videos, and mobile applications (Mea et al., 2016). Recent projects have already exemplified this trend by leveraging innovative social media strategies and proving that these boost public engagement and outreach (Williamson et al., 2024). Such a hybrid approach allows projects to reach both specialist and non-specialist audiences across multiple platforms, and it is the same approach that the project nextGEMS has implemented.

Finally, communication and dissemination activities also play a pivotal role in translating research findings into real-world outcomes, particularly through policy influence. For example, the SOPHIE project demonstrated how research-based communication can capture the attention of governments and stakeholders, leading to policy adaptations (Marín-González et al., 2017). nextGEMS had specific products to achieve the bridge towards policy, including the policy briefs (Sec. 5.3) and the science explainers (Sec. 4.6), as well as the active participation in events with the presence of policy-relevant stakeholders.

In summary, the pillars of nextGEMS communication and dissemination plan have been the following:

- A wide and diverse targeted audience
- A mix of traditional and innovative communication and dissemination tools
- Specific products and activities to reach the science-policy interface

The next subsections describe each.

3. nextGEMS audience

The communication and dissemination plan divided the audience into two groups: near-field and far-field stakeholder groups, and it adjusted the different communication and dissemination strategies to each of these groups.

1. The near-field nextGEMS stakeholder groups were formed by the following:
 - Scientists: earth science community and wider scientific community;
 - Users: users from renewable energy and fisheries;
 - Technologists: HPC technologists and high-capacity data experts;
2. The far-field nextGEMS stakeholder groups were formed by the following:
 - Policy-makers: policy and decision makers;
 - Broader user community: users from other sectors and domains, including climate services and met offices;

Figure 1: nextGEMS stakeholder groups and means and mediums of communication.

- Public and media: general public, including communities from West Africa, and journalists.

Figure 1 shows the communication and dissemination products that the project envisaged as relevant for each of these stakeholder groups. As mentioned previously, the nextGEMS communication strategy built upon two main ideas: tailoring communication and dissemination material to each stakeholder group and putting the emphasis on what is communicated as well as on the process of creating the message. These two ideas, the communication content and process, worked together synergistically, allowing us to reach more effectively the audience and increase the awareness about the development and results of the project, but also a robust legacy with the uptake of its outputs by different communities.

4. Traditional and innovative communication tools

nextGEMS implemented standard communication approaches by using the project website, social media, news articles and blogs, and word of mouth at various conferences and events. In addition, it implemented innovative communication formats: Vlog, science explainers, and storylines. These different product types can more effectively reach different audiences, as shown by the literature. In the next subsections we provide details about these tools.

4.1. Project website

The nextGEMS website (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>) serves as a central communication and dissemination platform for the project and is structured to provide both the scientific community and the general public with accessible, engaging, and regularly updated information. It is organized into several main sections: **“About”**, **“Research”**, **“News”**, **“Timeline”**, **“Resources”**, and **“Community Area”**, each tailored to showcase different facets of the project’s work, progress, and outcomes.

The **“About”** section offers an overview of the project’s vision, structure, and objectives, providing essential background information. It introduces the key project partners and institutions,

and outlines the overarching goals of nextGEMS in the context of advancing next-generation Earth system modeling.

The “**Research**” section highlights the scientific core of nextGEMS. It communicates the project’s key research questions, methodologies, and findings, and includes dedicated sub-pages for specific thematic areas. A strong emphasis is placed on making complex scientific content more accessible through the use of rich **visual media**, such as research videos, interactive graphics, and simplified Science Explainers. These visual materials are available both in the **media library** and embedded within relevant content pages, reflecting the project’s commitment to effective science communication.

The “**Community Area**” and related sub-pages feature collaborative aspects of the project, most notably the **nextGEMS Hackathons**. These events, held in various locations across Europe, are described in detail on their own page. The hackathons are portrayed not only as technical workshops, but as integral to the project’s co-creation and interdisciplinary exchange processes. This section also highlights outputs from the broader community, such as jointly authored publications, collaborative tools, and educational materials.

A notable feature of the website is the “**Timeline**” section, which tracks the project’s progress in alignment with predefined milestones. It offers a chronological overview of achievements, events, and key deliverables. Beyond simply listing milestones, this section incorporates multimedia elements — including videos that explain the project’s objectives and side events such as the **UCM Student Hackathon** — as well as creative outputs like **ScienceArt**, which was transformed into calendars and postcards to visually communicate climate science in an artistic way.

The “**Resources**” section serves as a hub for technical documentation, data access guidance, and software tools. It offers practical support for external researchers and stakeholders interested in working with nextGEMS outputs, thereby enhancing the usability and impact of the project’s data products.

To ensure clarity, usability, and visibility of key content, the website structure was periodically reviewed and reorganized. This iterative development allowed the project team to better highlight evolving priorities and make important updates easier to discover for returning users.

The “**News**” section was consistently maintained and updated throughout the project’s lifecycle. It features a combination of concise news updates and in-depth blog entries that document the project’s developments, highlight important events, and celebrate noteworthy achievements. This section played a vital role in fostering community engagement and ensuring transparent communication with stakeholders.

The nextGEMS website functions as a comprehensive and dynamic portal that reflects the project’s multifaceted activities. It effectively combines scientific depth with accessible presentation, fostering interaction among researchers, stakeholders, and the broader public. The following section of this report will provide a more detailed analysis of the published content and its role in outreach and community-building efforts.

Regarding the tracked impact of the nextGEMS website, three website metrics reports were compiled between July, 2024 and June, 2025 for the two main external communication chan-

nels: website and social media. In the case of the website, the metrics reports, although not extensive, are highly graphical and show who is interacting with nextGEMS’ content and how the community receives the information produced and transmitted by the project. To track the activity of website content such as blogposts, news, and landing pages, Wordpress offers its own web analytics platform, Matomo. This is the tool used for website reports.

The first metric report described the performance and engagement analytics between January, 2023 and June, 2024. The second metrics report was updated in October, 2024 for the period between July and August, 2024. Finally, the last metrics report was updated in July, 2025 for the period between September, 2024 and June, 2025.

However, nextGEMS values the data privacy of its audience. Hence, our analytical tools only capture limited personal details. It is likely that the metrics presented in this report only give a partial impression of the interactions with the created content and that our outreach activities could effectively have reached a larger audience than suggested by the data collected.

As of 2025, nearly 80% of nextGEMS website visitors are located in Europe (Fig. 2). The majority are based in Germany, the United Kingdom, and the Netherlands — together accounting for approximately 47% of all visitors.

Figure 2: Website visits by continent and country from September, 2024 to June, 2025. Source: Own creation.

Some key highlights of our website performance since 2023 are closely linked to various nextGEMS hackathons (Fig. 3). For instance, during the week of the Hamburg hackathon in 2023, our website recorded 260 visits, the highest number between January 2023 and June 2024. Similarly, between June 2024 and September 2025, a blog post about the Wageningen Hazard hackathon received 709 visits in its release week, marking a record high for that period. In other words, our online community demonstrates strong engagement with hackathon-related content on our website. For example, news articles providing live updates on the first or final hackathon day, as well as blog posts covering specific talks or topics featured during the hackathons.

Visits over time

Graph showing the daily fluctuation of visits. It was retrieved from the Wordpress metrics tool, Matomo Analytics.

Figure 3: Website visits graph from September, 2024 to June, 2025. Source: Own creation/Matomo.

4.2. News articles and blogs

In general, blog posts and news articles were created with the project's target audience (Sec. 3) in mind.

The *news articles* constitute shorter pieces of information, which were mainly used to spread organizational information for the hackathons, highlight current project developments, and promote creative output and scientific publications that were created by the nextGEMS community. In total, over 30 news articles were published, of which over 20 revolved around the five hackathons hosted and organized by nextGEMS institutions. These articles informed about the upcoming events, preparatory measures, and live updates throughout the hackathon weeks.

Blog posts paid more attention to newly published papers of the nextGEMS community, to summaries and recap the nextGEMS hackathons, and to inform about other project outputs, such as technical information or scientific videos that were created in collaboration with nextGEMS scientists. A total number of 25 blog posts have been created throughout the project's lifetime and additional blog posts are still due to be released until the end of August 2025. Blog posts about research papers were written in close collaboration with the researchers to ensure factual correctness through the use of precise and scientific terms, while keeping the content interesting, catchy, and easy to read or understand.

By the time of writing this report, a total of seven blog posts summarizing research papers recently published by nextGEMS scientists had been produced over the course of the project (Tab. 3). Additionally, six pieces on technical updates, five blog posts summarizing nextGEMS hackathons, and other content were published on the nextGEMS website. Blog posts were also used to highlight selected aspects of the website, such as the publications page. This page features the different types of publications that result from research conducted within the nextGEMS community. Previously, the project publications got little attention from website visitors. To generate more attention, a new blogpost segment, with the title "Brain Storms", was created. Twice a year, a blog post with an update on the latest publications of the nextGEMS community is

created, encouraging the readers to look at the other publications listed on the sub-page.

Table 3: Number of posts per content type on nextGEMS website.

Topic	Blogposts	News Articles	Total
Hackathons	5	22	27
Community Publications	7	2	9
Project Updates	2	6	8
Technical Updates	6	0	6
Videos	3	0	3
Creative Output	0	3	3

Each piece of content was first written in collaboration or by one member of the outreach team. It was then proofread by a nextGEMS member other than the author of the content, and paired with a catchy title and visualization, before being published on social media or the nextGEMS website.

4.3. Social media

To analyze nextGEMS' impact on its community, three metrics reports have been assembled since July 2024 for the two main external communication channels: the website and social media – which includes LinkedIn and Mastodon. The social media metrics reports are highly graphical and illustrate who is interacting with nextGEMS' content, as well as how the community receives the information produced and disseminated by the project.

The first metrics report described the performance and engagement on LinkedIn and Mastodon between January, 2023 and June, 2024. The second metrics report, updated in October, 2024, covered the period between July and August, 2024. Finally, the latest report was updated in July, 2025 and covers the period between September, 2024 and June, 2025.

Reporting on nextGEMS' social media channels (Fig. 4) is partly facilitated by the platforms themselves: LinkedIn provides its own analytics tool. Mastodon, by contrast, does not offer native analytics, making performance tracking more limited. Currently, the platform MastoMetrics is used to monitor metrics on the nextGEMS Mastodon account.

Some of the key highlights from our social media impact are illustrated in the first report: blog posts and live event updates about the Hamburg hackathon ranked among the best performing Mastodon posts. At the same time, social media content related to the Hamburg hackathon accounted for the highest organic engagement rate between July, 2023 and July, 2024. Simi-

Organic engagement rate

Organic, since we do not sponsor content.
Engagement rate is calculated as: (Clicks + Reactions + Comments + Shares + Follows) / Impressions

Figure 4: LinkedIn engagement rate timeline from September, 2024 to June, 2025. Source: Own creation.

larily, the latest report showed that the Wageningen Hackathon in October, 2024; the Stockholm Hackathon in March, 2025; and the Global Km-scale Hackathon in May, 2025 reached the highest engagement rates on our social media channels. This engagement pattern reflects the online community is actively interested in content aimed at providing updates on an ongoing event organized by nextGEMS (Fig. 5).

Other social media posts redirecting the audience to blogposts published on the nextGEMS website performed well in terms of views and impressions, according to data from the first metrics report. The blogposts aimed to inform about concepts, technicalities or climate phenomena, such as atmospheric blockings, the HEALpix grid, or tropical cyclone simulations. In short, besides the hackathon live updates, social media content aiming to inform about Climate Science and modelling topics related to nextGEMS achieved imminent results too.

Moreover, project videos directly published on LinkedIn and our many Science Art illustrations reached a significant engagement as well. For instance, the [post](#) disseminating a nextGEMS results video had 1,152 impressions, 646 views, and an average watching time of 27 seconds. In this case, video viewers were mostly laboratory scientists, research fellows, and students, accounting for approximately 33% of the total viewers altogether. University professors and software developers accounted for approximately 8% of total video viewers.

Generally, video engagement metrics showcase how nextGEMS social media content is constantly landing its main target audiences — such as scientists, users, and technologists —, while extending its reach to students and early-career professionals. However, nextGEMS has used different platforms to host the videos throughout the project, which might have affected the continuity and precise tracking of all video analytics.

LinkedIn is the only analytics tool used by nextGEMS social media team that allows detailed demographic tracking for followers, particularly regarding the audience’s occupations. These tool

Figure 5: Metrics of nextGEMS' LinkedIn best performing posts from September, 2024 to June, 2025. Source: Own creation.

enable the project to evaluate whether the social media content strategy is effectively reaching its targeted audiences. As of June, 2025, the majority of LinkedIn followers were researchers, representing 30.9% of our 1,089 followers (Fig. 6). Given that the primary target audience for nextGEMS communication channels has been defined as scientists, it is evident that social media platforms are effectively reaching this intended group.

Professionals in educational and engineering fields followed in second and third place, with 13.7% and 10.1% – respectively. Furthermore, the majority of our followers are based in Europe, with over 18% located in Germany, highlighting the strong presence of nextGEMS within the European Climate Science community (Fig. 7).

On LinkedIn, the “education” faction of nextGEMS followers may refer either to students enrolled in educational institutions or to individuals employed by them. Therefore, it is unclear what proportion of student followers are specifically engaging with nextGEMS content on LinkedIn. However, data on seniority shows that 32.6% of followers are at the entry level and 8.5% are trainees, which may include PhD students or early-career researchers (Fig. 8).

In addition, the main industries represented within our follower community are research services, which account for approximately 38%, and higher education, which represents around 24% (Fig. 9). These insights suggest that early-career professionals likely involved in research or education are increasingly engaging with our content. Other important sectors within the nextGEMS online community are environmental services, government organizations, and Information Technology (IT) services. This trend aligns with the societal goals of the project’s outreach strategy, as well as with the efforts to expand our impact to other audience segments in the past year.

Figure 6: Breakdown of LinkedIn followers by job function as of June, 2025. Source: Own creation.

Selection of content to be diffused on social media and website The performance of website sub-pages, blog posts, and news articles was checked on a regular basis using the Matomo Analytics Tool provided by the content management system WordPress. The least and best performing content is selected and promoted on social media or put into focus on the website.

For the selection of the least and best performing blog posts and news articles, the number of views and the date when the content was last disseminated on social media are compared. To promote the content, new social media posts are created, highlighting different aspects of the blog posts to attract more readers, increase the attention given to least performing posts, and retain the traction that the most popular content has generated.

All nextGEMS video materials (project goals, Science Explainers, research videos and specials) were successively diffused on LinkedIn and Mastodon to highlight key information about the project and to explain the ideas behind nextGEMS. If no new video content was created that needed to be diffused, previous videos were promoted a second time via a social media post that highlighted a different aspect of the content.

In addition to already existing content that is to be promoted, new content is created as follows.

Creation of social media content Regular social media posts (initially on Twitter until April 2024, on Mastodon since September 2023, on LinkedIn since February 2024) diffused blog posts, news articles, and other visual content, created for the website. Social media platforms were additionally used to highlight job opportunities and to promote upcoming events of the project. During such events (i.e the nextGEMS Hackathons) frequent social media updates were released in the manner of a “live-ticker” to keep the audience engaged and excited about

Followers' demographics (location)

Figure 7: Breakdown of LinkedIn followers by location as of June, 2025. Source: Own creation.

participating in hackathons in the future, in an attempt to grow the number of participants in the following years (Fig. 10).

At the start of each month, a post about the nextCalendArt artwork is released, giving a short description of the visible simulation or a related topic. The artwork was created by scientists of the nextGEMS project and consolidated into calendars or postcards by the project office. The goal of this creative output was to generate interest in climate phenomena in the wider population and to show the beauty of being creative with climate simulations.

A further segment of social media posts included interesting facts about the project. This segment was mainly active in 2023 but was still used on occasion in the following years. Some of the topics covered in this segment were: demographics of project members and institutions, importance of studying Earth system modelling, and sharing the current stage of the project.

The outreach team also occasionally incorporated informative posts about the Queer community (LGBTQIA2S+) in Climate Science to raise awareness for its members in the scientific workforce, and to highlight the disadvantages which Queer communities and other minorities face in the light of the climate crisis.

All social media posts were accompanied by a set of basic hashtags (e.g. #nextGEMS, #H2020, #stormresolving, #earthsystemmodelling) that can be applied to any post, and additional, more content-specific hashtags, such as #ICON, #IFS, #ScienceArt, etc. Additionally, partner institutes or single persons that are relevant for the topic, e.g. CINEA, EERIE, WarmWorld, Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, DKRZ, the creators of the nextCalendArt, etc., were tagged on the posts to create more visibility for both the post and the tagged entities.

In total, 138 posts were published on the platform X (former Twitter) from the start of the project

Figure 8: Breakdown of LinkedIn followers by seniority as of June, 2025. Source: Own creation.

until April 2024. After the takeover of Twitter by Elon Musk in 2022, nextGEMS decided to leave the platform and move to Mastodon instead in September 2023. Additionally, LinkedIn was used since the beginning of the project, however, the project's activities on this website could, due to limited analytical tools, only be tracked back until September 2023. Between September 2023 and July 2025 130 posts were published each on Mastodon and LinkedIn.

Publication of social media content During regular meetings, a content schedule was created featuring possible topics, upcoming events, and newly released papers. The outreach team decided which person should be responsible for writing and proofreading the individual items and the date by which this content needs to be released.

Blog posts and news articles were prepared on WordPress and uploaded to the website by the responsible person.

Social media posts were created via the social media management tool [Buffer](#) and scheduled to be released automatically. The releases were scheduled for specific dates and times during which most of the nextGEMS followers should be active on the social media platforms, such as in the morning and during their off-work hours. Additionally, relevant and interesting posts published by institutes inside and outside of the nextGEMS network were re-posted on occasion.

Due to the limited temporal capacities of the outreach team, occasional deviations from the set schedule occurred.

Limitations and lessons-learned First, as an answer to the changing dynamics on X after the acquisition of Elon Musk, the project office decided to switch from the platform formerly

Figure 9: Breakdown of LinkedIn followers by industry as of June, 2025. Source: Own creation.

called Twitter to Mattermost in 2024. Since there were disagreements in the Twitter community about whether to use alternative platforms and which ones to use instead, nextGEMS' already established scientific following could not be transferred to the alternative platform of Mastodon. As a result, the project's social media community could not grow continuously throughout the project's lifetime, which may have affected the level of views and, therefore, attention that social media posts and website content have received. Future projects should aim to continuously use one platform, enabling an organic development and growth of the project's audience and reach. Additionally, to leverage the potential to grow the projects' community, a stronger focus should be set on creating content for our target audiences and adjusting content and outreach strategies to better reach those groups of people who are least engaged with the created content.

Second, given the technical nature of the project, mostly the scientific community was targeted, but an additional effort was made to reach other groups. Occasional posts, such as the regularly released nextCalendArt were especially targeted at the non scientific community, highlighting the visual appeal of climate simulations, rather than the technical or scientific background. Future projects could consider to work more actively on acquiring new followers and spreading the word outside of the scientific community. Activities such as re-posting relevant topics from other research institutions or renowned researchers and decision- and policy-makers could be one way of achieving this. Interactions with the community and externals in the form of commenting and re-posting topic or field-related posts could further increase the engagement with the project's content. To address important topics of the wider climate science community and to attract new people and institutes to the project, the incorporation of frequent social media posts (or re-posts) about important historic events, anniversaries and international days related to climate topics, e.g. [The International Day of Clean Energy](#) on Jan. 26, [The International Day of Clean Air for blue skies](#) on Sept. 7. and the [COP29](#) in November 2024, could be additionally beneficial.

Third, the social media and website activities were mainly conducted by members of the project office who had a limited background in social media management or communication. To support

Figure 10: Number of posts per topic, published on the social media platforms Mastodon and LinkedIn between September 2023 and July 2025

these members in their daily tasks, to improve the teams' skills working with social media and engaging target audiences, and to maximise the impact of the nextGEMS outreach activities, the project provided opportunities to attend different workshops. These workshops were supported by the [MAIA project](#), which is an EU-funded project that works on connecting communities, platforms, knowledge and research in the field of climate change. Additionally, the Max-Planck Institute for Meteorology offered a two-day workshop on science communication with an external coach.

4.4. Conferences and events

The key platform for collaboration in the framework of nextGEMS are hackathons (more details in the report for D10.5, Konow et al., 2025), but nextGEMS consortium members also actively participate in other events, including scientific conferences (such as EGU and AGU general assemblies, or ECCA), expert events (e.g. examples from Africa) or other events, such as the WWRP/SERA "Weather and Society" online conference in 2022.

A list of conference contributions can be found in the Appendix B.

4.5. Vlogs

The project has produced different types of videos, overall labeled as 'Vlogs' (Tab. 5). With 52 published videos, nextGEMS has made sure to maintain high project visibility and effective communication to all its target stakeholder groups during the course of the project.

Target Audiences of the Videos

Project Goal – In a Nutshell: This short animated video (approx. 2 minutes) delivers a clear

Table 5: Overview of available videos per type.

Type of Video	Goal	Videos by Researcher
Project Goal - In a nutshell	Animated video of 2 min lengths that provides an overview of the project in terms of overall goal and method and highlights its innovative character.	Scripted and Animated Video
Project Goal	These videos aim at providing the overall goal of the project targeted at the wider scientific community.	Björn Stevens
		Irina Sandu
Workstream Goals	In this videos the Workstream leaders present the individual goals of the respective workstream: Storms and Society, Storms and Land, Storms and Radiation, Storms and Ocean.	Dragana Bojovic
		Noel Keenlyside
		Heike K. and Daniel K.
		Frida Bender
		Cathy Hohenegger
Community Videos Hackathons	In these videos we captured the community collaborating at hackathons. Whereas the other videos are more targeted towards the external stakeholders, this video format fostered the team spirit and helped the distributed teams to better identify themselves with the nextGEMS project.	Berlin
		Vienna
		Madrid
		Hamburg
		Wageningen
		Stockholm
Research Videos	For selected journal publications we produced Research Videos. Journal publications have proven to be an effective tool for our peer group. However, in order to convey the content of the journals to a wider audience, we produce videos where we share the content in a structured video.	Hamburg
		Hans Seguara
		Marta Waclawczyk
		Eulalia Baulenas
		Marta Mrozowska
Science Explainer	The videos are concise, visually engaging, and presented in clear, accessible language.	Hans S., Imme B., Xabier P., Thomas R., Sebastian M., Edgar D.
		Philip Stier and Philipp Weiss
		Chiel van Heerwaarden
		Eulalia Baulenas
Specials	Tido Semmler emphasizing the importance of science communication.	Thomas R. and Xabier P.
	Björn Stevens interviewing Masaki Satoh as a pioneer in km scale modeling.	Imme Benedict
		Tido Semmler
		Masaki S. and Bjorn S.
Bio Videos	In this short clips we introduced individual scientists and their contribution to the project.	Emanuel Dutra
		Bjorn Stevens
		Hans Segura
		Yuting Wu
		Elsa Mohino
		Marius Winkler
		Dragana Bojovic
		Simona Bordoni
		Thomas Rackow
		Jonathan Wille
		Tobias Kölling
		Divya Praturi
		Johann Jungclaus
		Julian Asbäck
		Heike Konow
		Rumeng Li
		Martina Klose
Jiawei Bao		
Jana Seipelt		
Workstream Results	In this videos the Workstream leaders present the results of the respective workstream: Storms and Society, Storms and Land, Storms and Radiation, Storms and Ocean.	Dragana Bojovic
		Noel Keenlyside
		Heike K. and Eulalia B.
		Frida Bender
Overall View on the Project	Björn Stevens places the results of the nextGEMS project in the larger context of the development of climate research and climate modelling.	Cathy Hohenegger
		Björn Stevens

and engaging overview of the project's aims and innovative methodologies. Designed for newcomers and a general audience, it serves as an ideal entry point to understand the core mission of nextGEMS.

Project Goal: These videos provide a more in-depth explanation of the overall objectives of nextGEMS, targeted at the broader scientific community. They are suitable for academic peers, research institutions, and policy stakeholders seeking to understand the strategic vision of the project.

Workstream Goals: Each video in this category features a workstream leader presenting the specific goals of their thematic area (Storms and Society, Storms and Land, Storms and Radiation, Storms and Ocean). These are intended for both internal project members and external scientific audiences interested in domain-specific insights.

Community Videos – Hackathons: These videos capture the collaborative spirit and dynamics of the project during hackathons. Aimed primarily at internal teams, they helped foster identity, cohesion, and a sense of shared purpose among distributed groups across the project.

Research Videos: Designed to communicate the content of selected journal publications in a structured and visual manner, these videos make complex scientific findings accessible to a broader audience beyond the academic community, including science communicators and informed public stakeholders.

Science Explainer Videos: These concise and visually engaging videos explain scientific concepts in clear and accessible language. They are ideal for students, educators, policymakers, and the wider public looking to understand key scientific topics related to climate modeling.

Specials: These feature prominent figures such as Tido Semmler and Björn Stevens addressing themes like the importance of science communication or reflecting on pioneering work in kilometer-scale modeling. These interviews and commentaries are valuable for both the scientific community and science outreach professionals.

Bio Videos: Short clips introducing individual scientists and their contributions to nextGEMS. These humanize the project and highlight personal stories, making them suitable for public engagement and showcasing the team behind the research.

Workstream Results: These videos present the outcomes of each workstream, structured similarly to the goal videos. They are primarily intended for the scientific community and stakeholders interested in research impact and deliverables.

Overall View on the Project: In this reflective piece, Björn Stevens situates the nextGEMS project within the broader development of climate research and modeling. This video is especially relevant for high-level stakeholders, policymakers, and strategic partners who are interested in the long-term significance of the project.

Results Video: this type of video shows the on-going research in layman terms, and it is meant to reach far-field stakeholders interested in the advancement of climate science. nextGEMS simulations are fascinating demonstrations of the latest scientific achievements (Fig. 11). Their visual appeal, together with the Vlog's video outputs, has jointly provided a very robust strategy

to achieving the main goals of the communication and dissemination plan.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the results video

4.6. Science Explainers

Science explainers present the driving ideas and progress from nextGEMS scientists in plain language. The explainers aim to show how scientists think and their way of working. The aim was to show the inception and development of research ideas, until their ultimate outcomes, which would be traditionally presented in peer-reviewed articles. The science explainers cover a wide range of topics relevant to any audience interested in the latest breakthroughs related to storm-resolving earth-system-models. This approach gives access to information and explanations that are often not otherwise available to the public. WP10 developed a template and guidance for preparing science explainers. Through collaboration between project scientists and Storms & Society theme, the project has so far published several science explainers, including:

- Tracking fast-forming and dissipation clouds
- Knowledge networks in NextGEMS
- Scientific and technical challenges of extending a weather model for climate studies
- Understanding aerosols and clouds with storm-resolving simulations
- Tackling the biases of tropical mixed layer depth in ocean models
- Retuning the ocean vertical mixing scheme for storm-resolving models

The science explainers are presented in different formats (e.g., blog post, brochure and nextGEMS progress videos). This diversity of formats helps reach different stakeholder communities from the nextGEMS far-field, such as broader user community, public, media, or policy-makers. Although the target audience for this type of message are mainly far-field nextGEMS stakeholder groups, it also can provide near-field groups with updates on the progress in the project.

More details can be read in the report for Deliverable 10.9 (Bojovic and Baulenas, 2024).

4.7. Storylines

Storylines can be presented in various formats, e.g., web-explorable story-maps, combining text, images and maps with geo-referenced data and simulation output. This type of material is especially adequate for near-field stakeholder groups, the target audience of the nextGEMS storylines, as it involves users additionally in its co-development process.

For instance, for the energy storylines a platform was created with GIS displaying the nextGEMS simulations together with important geo data, such as the network distribution, the energy demand of the Spanish peninsula, as well as the current distribution of wind and solar parks. This platform supported greatly in communicating the relevance of km-scale. Stakeholders also appreciated the explanations about the differences between the models (ICON and IFS-FESOM), which helped them understand the differences they were seeing in the maps.

As an additional strategy related to the communication using as scientific products the storylines, we also used summary reports, progress videos, conference presentations and journal publications to communicate the key storyline findings to a broader audience and policymakers (see D10.7 and D10.8 for detailed reports on the two storylines). In particular, the fishery storyline that applied nextGEMS data to better understand marine ecosystem dynamics and changes in the Atlantic Ocean off the west coast of Africa targeted stakeholders and policymakers from this part of the world. These are some of the events where the elements of this storyline were presented, and in which important stakeholders including policy-makers attended:

- Inaugural African Ocean Week and the 3rd High-Level Ministerial Conference on the Blue Belt Initiative (BBI), October 2024, Tangier, Morocco. The events were attended by representatives from 32 countries, including the African Union commissioner, representatives of the EU DG MARE, and FAO.
- African Consultation in Preparation for the 3rd United Nations Ocean Conference (UNOC-3); October 2024;
- Conference of Fisheries Ministers of the Sub-Regional Fisheries Committee (SRFC) countries, October 2024.

5. Other communication approaches to reach the science-policy and the science-society interfaces

Project partners are encouraged to express their creativity and communicate their work to broader audience via video, text, or a piece of art in a form of figure or climate visualization.

5.1. Training

Project scientists received a training to produce videos, which should further enhance this effective communication approach. The goal of the “NextGEMS Video Training Material” was to help researchers improve their communication skills—particularly through video production—in

order to effectively disseminate their research to a broader audience, including the general public, the wider scientific community, and policy makers. The training emphasized moving beyond traditional publication methods toward more engaging and accessible formats.

Structure of the Training Material:

Introduction to Video as a Medium: The material began by addressing the existing gap in dissemination between researchers and wider audiences. It explored how video could serve as a bridge to close this communication divide.

Video Production Basics: The training covered the fundamentals of video production, including different types of camera shots (long shot, close-up, medium shot), camera angles (high angle, low angle, eye level), and composition principles such as the rule of thirds.

Technical Aspects: Participants received detailed guidance on technical elements such as lighting, audio, and the importance of understanding resolution and frame rates. The training also offered equipment recommendations tailored to different budget levels (low, medium, and high).

Script Development: Researchers were guided in developing a script that clearly outlined their research question, methodology, findings, relevance, and future outlook. This structured approach ensured that the key messages of their research were communicated effectively.

Practice and Feedback: The training included practical exercises such as dry runs and rehearsals that focused on time management, facial expressions, and gestures. It emphasized the value of peer feedback to refine both the content and delivery of the video presentations.

Post-Production and Dissemination: Guidance was provided on editing videos and choosing appropriate dissemination platforms (e.g., YouTube, social media) to maximize reach and impact. The training also highlighted how to define and analyze Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of the video content.

How the Training Helped Researchers:

Enhanced Communication Skills: By focusing on video production, researchers learned to communicate their work in a visually appealing and accessible way, making their findings more understandable to non-expert audiences.

Broader Reach: The use of video enabled researchers to reach beyond their academic circles, connecting with the public and decision makers and thus increasing the societal impact of their research.

Practical Skills: The training offered hands-on experience with video production, including how to work with low-cost equipment—an especially valuable aspect for researchers with limited resources.

Structured Presentation: The emphasis on script writing and presentation structure helped researchers clarify their core message and communicate it more effectively and engagingly.

In summary, the training equipped researchers with the skills and knowledge to use video as a powerful tool for research dissemination and engagement.

5.2. Visual communication with nextCalendarArt

Visual communication is another strong communication element of nextGEMS. Numerous climate visualization videos, presenting outputs from nextGEMS models in an attractive way, have been published at the website and on social media.

Art is an important and increasingly used form of scientific expression. To boost the artistic spirit, nextGEMS organizes a competition of science-based visualization pieces each year. The best figures make it into the calendar 'nextCalendarArt' (Fig. 12). The calendars for 2022, 2023, and 2024 were distributed to the nextGEMS consortium and friends. These calendars can be accessed through Zenodo (Mieslinger et al., 2022; Wu, 2023; Wu, 2024).

Figure 12: Example for nextGEMS Calendar Art for the year 2024

In 2025, a special set of nextGEMS postcards was produced, featuring some of the most popular and visually striking artistic creations from previous years. These postcards served both as a creative showcase and a communication tool, and were distributed at various events (Seipelt, 2025).

5.3. Policy briefs

Policy briefs represent a key component of nextGEMS' communication and dissemination strategy aimed at engaging policy-makers and decision-makers at national and European levels. Designed to translate complex scientific insights into accessible and actionable messages, the policy briefs serve as a bridge between the project's technical outputs and the information needs of the policy community. They complement other dissemination efforts by offering tailored content that highlights the societal relevance and policy implications of storm-resolving Earth sys-

tem modeling. The topics addressed in the policy briefs were selected based on both scientific advancements and stakeholder relevance, with early drafts focusing on themes such as building user communities around next-generation Earth system models and the importance of hackathons to achieve it. By integrating policy briefs into the broader communication strategy, nextGEMS ensured that its results not only reach the scientific community but also inform policy discussions and support evidence-based decision-making.

More information can be found in the report for D10.10 (Bojovic and Baulenas, 2025).

6. Internal communication channels

Internally, nextGEMS project partners benefit from communication through mailing list and platforms such as Mattermost, which allows for opening several chats by selected topics. An important arena for regular internal communication and for maintaining strong collaborative relationships is the weekly office hour. The office hour is coordinated by early career scientists (ECS), who select a different project related topic and speaker each week. This helps keep the contact between scientists, in particular ECS, as well as to follow the latest developments in the project in a participatory and fun way.

7. Dissemination Through Strategic Multipliers: Leveraging the idw Platform

In our dissemination strategy for nextGEMS, we effectively leveraged the Informationsdienst Wissenschaft (idw) platform (<https://idw-online.de>) and its news portal (<https://nachrichten.idw-online.de>) to promote video content.

idw is a leading science communication network in the German-speaking region, connecting over 1,000 scientific institutions—including universities, research institutes, and science organizations. It provides a trusted and widely used platform for publishing news, events, and multimedia from the academic and research community. With a reach extending to journalists, educators, policymakers, and the interested public, idw acts as a highly effective multiplier: when content is published on the platform, it is automatically distributed via targeted mailing lists, RSS feeds, and search functionalities used by media outlets and stakeholders across sectors.

This significantly enhanced the visibility of our videos and announcements beyond our own communication channels, helping us reach new audiences and amplify the impact of our messages across the scientific and media landscape.

8. Conclusion

The project communication and dissemination activities follow the principles of visibility, transparency, plurality and usability. This includes ensuring visibility of the project and its outcomes for a wide range of stakeholder circles; being transparent on the evolution of the nextGEMS scientific production; plurality in the perspectives included and reached with the different communication and dissemination products; and usability by tailoring the scientific outputs with and for different stakeholder groups and using communication approaches for starting knowledge coproduction. Particularly interesting are nextGEMS's three innovative communication and engagement approaches: videos, science explainers and storylines. Developing target group oriented videos, nextGEMS tailored them to all six stakeholder groups targeted by the project.

At the conclusion of the project, the project has produced 56 blogs, 52 videos, 2 communication trainings, 7 science explainers, two storylines and two policy briefs. The blogs reported on conducted activities, informed about upcoming activities (e.g. Hackathon registrations), or pointed out at other communication products, such as video-recorded science explainers. The videos were short, visually appealing, and were prepared in an accessible language. This format is considered an extremely powerful communication tool, that can be easily disseminated through social media, showcased at events or distributed in other ways, and well received by different audiences independently of their technical and scientific backgrounds as shown with the social media metrics. The science explainers also offered a powerful communication tool, showing the driving ideas and progress from nextGEMS scientists in plain language and different formats. Finally, an important approach for disseminating project outcomes has been through storylines. The co-exploration and co-design activities allowed communicating the scientific breakthroughs that the project offered in climate science to a diverse audience. This work has been detailed in the reports for D10.7 (Brehmer et al., 2025) and D10.8 (Baulenas et al., 2025).

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Appendices

A. List of communication activities

A.1. Science Explainers

- Storms & Society – Knowledge networks in nextGEMS ([Video](#), [Factsheet](#))
- Model Development – Challenges in model development ([Video](#), [Factsheet](#))
- Storms & Land – Tracking fast-forming and dissipating clouds ([Video](#), [Factsheet](#))
- Storms & Ocean – Tackling the biases of tropical mixed layer: depth ([Factsheet](#))
- Storms & Ocean – Ocean mixing in nextGEMS: ([Factsheet](#))
- Storms & Land – Modelling the water cycle over land ([Video](#))
- Storms & Radiation – Aerosol modelling in storm-resolving models ([Video](#), [Factsheet](#))

A.2. Blogposts

- Caroline Muller breaks down the physics of big storms at the Global Km-scale Hackathon ([blogpost](#))
- Observing extreme winds and possible renewable energy applications for nextGEMS ([blogpost](#))
- The Future of Climate Modeling: Insights from the nextGEMS Hazard Hackathon ([blogpost](#))
- Introducing Easy Gems: your gateway to Next-Generation climate modelling ([blogpost](#))
- Weaker land–atmosphere coupling in global storm-resolving simulation ([blogpost](#))
- Using Machine Learning to identify climate models ([blogpost](#))
- The Role of Aerosols in our Climate: Insights from the nextGEMS Project ([blogpost](#))
- The Joint Venture of EVE & CORDEX ([blogpost](#))
- Research video: Understanding precipitation in the tropics ([blogpost](#))
- The mechanisms underlying the tropical Pacific surface warming ([blogpost](#))
- Research video: Studying Atmospheric Turbulence ([blogpost](#))
- The Earth system models used in nextGEMS, explained ([blogpost](#))
- Reviving some special moments of our 4th km-scale Hackathon in Hamburg ([blogpost](#))
- Assessing daily temperature variability in the nextGEMS storm-resolving models ([blogpost](#))
- Research video: Exploring storylines in Climate Science ([blogpost](#))
- Of hierarchies, chunking, and HEALPix ([blogpost](#))
- Advancing tropical cyclone simulations for improved climate predictions and resilience ([blogpost](#))
- Diversity and collaboration at our 4th km-scale Hackathon in Hamburg ([blogpost](#))
- Understanding the impact of climate change on ocean eddy activity ([blogpost](#))
- Bridging climate, energy, and society: testing applications of high-resolution earth system models to societal challenges ([blogpost](#))

- nextGEMS Challenge Problems ([blogpost](#))
- High-frequency data logging station list ([blogpost](#))
- Updated nextGEMS models for the next simulation cycle ([blogpost](#))
- Fixing the water and energy budget imbalances in ECMWF's Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) ([blogpost](#))

A.3. News (Excerpt)

- WCRP's global km-scale climate modeling hackathon: The nextGEMS legacy goes global! ([news](#))
- The Stockholm hackathon ended with an integrated Climate Science community ([news](#))
- Renewable energy, new simulations, and newcomers at nextGEMS' final hackathon in Stockholm ([news](#))
- nextGEMS' 5th Hazard Hackathon gathers over 80 participants in Wageningen for an exciting challenge ([news](#))
- Brain Storms: Exploring nextGEMS publications of the second half of 2023 ([news](#))
- Brain Storms: Exploring the scientific work of nextGEMS in the first half of 2023 ([news](#))
- 5th nextGEMS Hackathon x WUR x Uni Bern ([news](#))
- Reflecting on the grand finale: highlights from our 4th km-scale Hackathon's closing session ([news](#))
- Our 4th km-scale Hackathon started: what happened on the first day? ([news](#))
- All you need to know about our 4th km-scale Hackathon ([news](#))
- What is nextGEMS doing right now? ([news](#))
- nextGEMS turns two! ([news](#))
- Cycle 3 Hackathon ([news](#))
- Mini-hackathon S&L ([news](#))
- nextGEMS turns one! ([news](#))
- S&O summer slackathon ([news](#))
- Cycle 2 Hackathon([news](#))
- 1st place in the HGF scientific image contest! ([news](#))
- UCM Student Hackathon ([news](#))
- New design and community identity ([news](#))
- nextGEMS goes Levante ([news](#))
- nextGEMS Art turns into the nextCalendArt 2022! ([news](#))
- nextGEMS Art ([news](#))
- Cycle 1 Hackathon ([news](#))
- nextGEMS-Project officially starts with a Kick-Off Meeting on 1st September 2021 ([news](#))

B. Conference contributions

Oral presentations

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- Kuma, P. (2024b). “Climate Modelling and Current Research Topics in Climate Science”. Lecture Series in High Performance Computing, National Competence Center for HPC, Bratislava, Slovakia (online). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14009718.
- Li, R., P. Weiss, A. Baer, C. Pérez García-Pando, P. Stier, and M. Klose (2025). “Unveiling global haboob behavior with a kilometer-scale aerosol-climate model”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-11001.
- Martín-Rey, M., B. Rodríguez-Fonseca, T. Losada, A. Prigent, I. Polo, A. Abi, E. Mohino, L. Montoya-Carramolino, E. Calvo-Miguélez, J. Wu, and D. Putrasahan (2025). “Driving mechanisms of Atlantic Niño under different vertical ocean resolutions”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-8915.

- Müller, S. K. and S. Bordoni (2025). “Understanding tropical precipitation biases in kilometer-scale global climate models using the atmospheric energy balance framework”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-11818.
- Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, X., T. Becker, S. Milinski, T. Rackow, I. Sandu, S. Boussetta, E. Dutra, I. Hadade, J. Martins, J. McNorton, B. Sützl, and N. Wedi (2024). “Demonstrating the potential of km-scale multi-annual coupled global simulations in nextGEMS: a (urban) surface perspective”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-8254.
- Poschlod, B., L. Brunner, B. Blanz, and L. Klufft (2025). “Output regridding can lead to Moiré pattern in km-scale global climate model data from ICON”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-15826.
- Praturi, D. S. and C. Hohenegger (2025). “Projected changes to the intertropical convergence zone in warming scenario global storm resolving simulations”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-10328.
- Praturi, D. S. and B. Stevens (2024). “On the vorticity statistics in the Atlantic and East Pacific ITCZ”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-4564.
- Rackow, T., T. Becker, R. Ghosh, A. Koldunov, X. Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, and D. Takasuka (2025). “Multi-year simulations at kilometre scale with the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to FESOM2.5 and NEMOv3.4”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-6699.
- Rackow, T., T. Becker, X. Pedruzo Bagazgoitia, I. Sandu, L. Zampieri, F. Ziemer, and ECMWF-AWI Team (2022). “Storm-resolving simulations with IFS-NEMO/FESOM in the NextGEMS project”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu22-10757.
- Raj, J., E. Mohino Harris, M. B. Rodriguez de Fonseca, and T. Losada Doval (2024). “Impact Of Ocean Layer Thickness on The Simulation Of African Easterly Waves in High-Resolution Coupled General Circulation Model Simulations”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-20067.
- Rieger, V., P. Splechtna, and A. Voigt (2024). “Identifying cloud objects in the km-scale earth system model ICON”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-5731.
- Sarre, A. (2024a). “How to foster international collaboration with Africa starting with IPCC and including initiative as nextGEMS”. 7-8 October 2024, Tangier, Morocco.
- (2024b). “What are the latest research findings on how climate change will impact specifically pelagic resources in West Africa”. 9 October 2024, Tangier, Morocco.
- Spät, D., D. Schuhbauer, and A. Voigt (2023). “Characteristics of African Sahel Precipitation in global storm-resolving Climate Models”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-13727.
- Spät, D., A. Voigt, M. Biasutti, and D. Schuhbauer (2024). “Autocorrelation — A Simple Diagnostic for Tropical Precipitation in Global Kilometer-Scale Climate Models”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-9221.
- Tuppi, L., M. Ekblom, D. Köhler, P. Ollinaho, and H. J. Järvinen (2024). “Algorithmic optimisation of key parameters of OpenIFS: Implications on ensemble forecasts”. Presented at EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-7246.
- Veerman, M. and C. van Heerwaarden (2024). “Surface irradiance variability over land in storm-resolving models.” DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-19072.
- Widmann, H., C. Wickramage, and F. Wachsmann (2025). “Implementing FAIR Principles for Earth System Data: Insights from the European Eddy-Rich Earth-System Models (EERIE) project”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-21162.
- Wille, J. and E. Fischer (2024). “Representation of extreme precipitation events in storm-resolving global climate models within the nextGEMS project”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-11797.
- (2025). “Dry spell representation on regional and global scale using convection-permitting models within the nextGEMS project”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-17833.
- Ziemer, F., T. Kölling, and L. Klufft (2024). “Data access for km-scale resolution models”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-18256.

Poster presentations

- Baulenas, E., G. Versteeg, M. Terrado, J. Mindlin, and D. Bojovic (2023a). “Assembling the climate story: use of storyline approaches in climate-related science”. Presented at EGU General Assembly 2023. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-1417.
- Bordoni, S., R. D’Agostino, and A. M. Tompkins (2022). “Tropical precipitation biases in storm-resolving Earth System Models”.
- Chandrasekar, A., A. Marx, S. Müller, E. Sharifi, J. Javier Leal Rojas, and S. Thober (2023). “Assessing future water availability using HydroRiver – A use case in the climate adaptation digital twin of the Destination Earth Program”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-5087.
- Dengler, M., T. Fischer, M. Jochum, V. Stockmeyer, H. Melzer, M. Mrozowska, J. Jungclaus, B. Bastin, and A. Koldunov (2023). “Mixing processes in the upper tropical Atlantic: An event data base for evaluating vertical mixing parameterizations in Earth System Models”. Poster presentation, Oct. 24, 16:00–18:00. WCRP Open Science Conference, PC 14: Ocean mixing and climate, Kigali, Rwanda.
- Fróis, L., P. M. A. Miranda, and E. Dutra (2023). “Diurnal to interannual variability in Cabauw simulated by the ECLand land surface model”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-9920.
- Gärtner, J., U. Proske, N. Brüggemann, O. Gutjahr, H. Haak, D. Putrasahan, and K.-H. Wieners (2025). “A case for open communication of bugs in climate models”. Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-20866.
- Ghinassi, P. and P. Davini (2024). “The representation of tropical cyclones in high resolution coupled climate simulations”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-2040.
- Jungclaus, J., D. Putrasahan, S. Bastin, and M.-S. Specht (2023). “Atmospheric response to Tropical Instability Waves in high-resolution coupled NextGEMS simulations”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-7838.
- Kuma, P., F. Bender, and A. R. Jönsson (2023). “Climate Model Code Genealogy and Its Relation to Climate Feedbacks and Sensitivity”. Presented at AGU Annual Meeting, San Francisco (Dec 2023) and online (Jan 2024).
- Kuma, P. and F. A.-M. Bender (2023). “Using ship observations to assess Southern Ocean clouds in a storm-resolving general circulation model ICON”. Presented at 15th Bolin Days, Stockholm, Sweden. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10956026.
- (2024). “Using ship observations to assess Southern Ocean clouds in a storm-resolving general circulation model ICON”. Presented at Swedish Climate Symposium, Norrköping, Sweden. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11204414.
- Kuma, P., F. A.-M. Bender, and A. R. Jönsson (2023b). “Climate Model Code Genealogy and Its Relation to Climate Feedbacks and Sensitivity”. Presented at Cloud Feedback Model Intercomparison Project Meeting, Paris, France.
- (2023c). “Climate model code genealogy and its relation to sensitivity and feedbacks”. Presented at 28th IUGG General Assembly, Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.57757/IUGG23-0509.
- Lacima, A., K. Grayson, R. Chavez, G. Versteeg, N. Gonzalez-Reviriego, F. J. Doblas-Reyes, and A. Soret (2023). “Heat waves in urban environments - A Destination Earth use case in the Climate Adaptation Digital Twin”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-10107.
- Lanteri, P. and S. Bordoni (2025). “Mediterranean extreme precipitation events in storm-resolving NextGEMS Earth System Models”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-9160.
- Modali, K., K. Peters-von Gehlen, F. Ziemann, R. Saini, S. Grasse, and M. Schultz (2024). “A cascaded framework for unified access to and analysis of kilometer scale global simulations across a federation of data centers”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-19677.
- Nazarova, N., J. von Hardenberg, P. Davini, M. Nurisso, S. Caprioli, and P. Ghinassi (2024). “Evaluating Tropical Precipitation Extremes: Insights from first simulations from nextGEMS and Destination Earth Climate Digital Twin”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-11498.
- Rackow, T., X. Pedruzo Bagazgoitia, T. Becker, S. Milinski, I. Sandu, M. Diamantakis, H. F. Goessling, I. Hadade, J. Hegewald, N. Koldunov, A. Koldunov, T. Kölling, K. Mogensen, D. Sidorenko, J. Streffing, N. Wedi, L. Zampieri, and F. Ziemann (2023). “Storm- and eddy-resolving simulations with IFS-FESOM/NEMO at the kilometre scale”. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-16453.

- Tuppi, L., M. Ekblom, P. Ollinaho, and H. J. Järvinen (2023). "Algorithmic Optimisation of Key Parameters of OpenIFS: Implications on Ensemble Forecasts". Presented at EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-4817.
- Wille, J. and E. Fischer (2023). "Dynamical representation of extreme precipitation events in storm resolving global climate models within the NextGEMS project". DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu23-8455.
- Zimmermann, J., F. Ziemer, and T. Kölling (2024). "Data access patterns of km-scale resolution models". DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17150.